

E Content – Educational Material

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Abstract:

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become one of the building blocks of modern society. Many countries now include mastering the basic ICT skills as well as 21st century skills (Communication, Collaboration, Creativity, Critical Thinking and Problem Solving) as part of the core of basic education, along with reading, writing and arithmetic. ICT has undoubtedly brought a revolution that has the immense potential to provide more engaging, collaborative and experiential learning platforms. Since the youth constitute more than 67% of the Indian population, it is mandatory to design a curriculum that aids skill development of youth along with providing quality basic education. The present government also emphasises on skill development and use of ICT for empowering the youth. The Digital India campaign (2015) has emerged as a synonym for technology revolution in India. To achieving the triple goals of Digital India Campaign i.e., skill, scale and speed the use of ICT is the way out. The government of India seeks to strengthen the use of ICT in almost every sphere and hence the campaign is centered on three key areas – digital infrastructure available for every citizen, governance and services on demand and digital empowerment of citizens. The National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in School.

Keywords: Technology, Technology, importance, E-Learning, Digital Research

Introduction:

ICT refers to the convergence of technologies that allow for the collection, storage, processing, transmission, and presentation of information. It encompasses nearly every type of business today and relies on ICT workers

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The National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in School Education (2012) developed by Ministry of Human

Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India further emphasizes in its mission statement “to devise, catalyze, support and sustain ICT and ICT enabled activities and process in order to improve access, quality and efficiency in the school system”. Therefore, the education system is moving toward harnessing the potential of ICT to serve the three cardinal principles of access, equity and quality. New integrated scheme – Samagra Siksha (2018) rolled out by Department of School Education and Literacy, MHRD, Govt of India while advocating for imparting quality school education and teacher education has emphasized on providing quality eContent as a pre-requisite for integrating ICT in Education.

eContent augments the learning experience by deploying various media for visualization and explanation of abstract ideas. Keeping in view the diverse needs of learners,

now use of eContent has become an essential component of the teaching and learning processes. eContent is available in large numbers through various sources, but few of them are found to have the desired quality in terms of content, pedagogy as well as technical aspects. Copyright violations are rampant thereby restricting the scope of customising the eContent according to the local needs. Also with plethora of smart and mobile devices, teacher and student driven eContents are available in abundance in the market. eContents are prepared by agencies and organisations as well as individuals. In this situation, quality of such eContents may be questionable; hence it is important to develop clear guidelines for preparing quality and standard eContent.

The Department of School Education and Literacy (DSE&L) MHRD, Govt. of India had set up a committee to deliberate on this issue and delineate guidelines to be used by various stakeholders.

Guidelines for Development of eContent for School Education to enable planning, preparation, curation and dissemination of quality digital contents for school and teacher education. A list of experts involved for development of guidelines is annexed as Annexure - V. As part of this exercise, two workshops were organized involving experts from NCERT, SCERTs, various universities, NCTE, CBSE, NIOS, NGOs, Corporate sector, practising teachers etc. Based on these deliberations, a guideline providing the details of the process of developing eContent has been developed.

The various phases of the eContent development process are as follows:- analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation. The specific activities of each phase are also clearly defined in the guidelines. It also provides the parameters for assessing the quality of eContent during the process of development as

well as curation by various stakeholders like organisations, administrators, teachers and students.

Guidelines for Developing eContent:

eContent is any form of learning material available digitally which a learner access or interacts with so as to achieve related learning outcomes. eContent is becoming popular because it allows flexibility in terms of time, place and pace of learning. A resource rich environment is necessary for teaching and learning to be effective. However, many of the educational resources are not easily accessible because of issues related to copyright. Hence, there is a movement to produce learning resources and make them available with open licenses which are known as Open Educational Resources (OER). Open Educational Resources (OER) are freely available. Openly licensed materials and media are useful for teaching, learning and assessing as well as for research purposes. Wide variety of OER is available for free use for teachers, instructors, researchers and students. If used appropriately, digital learning resources can add considerable value to the quality of teaching and to the learners' experience. eContent is often made up of separate units or a combination of text, video, images and sound. These are the building blocks which are often used to make composite learning objects that can be exhibited in various presentation formats.

Process of developing eContent:

eContent design, development depends upon the nature of the content and its target learners. It will also depend on the quality and complexity of the learning to be achieved. Instructional design is the practice of creating instructional experiences that make the acquisition of knowledge and skill more efficient, effective and appealing. The process broadly

consists of determining the current status of learners' understanding, defining the end goal of the instructional material and creating some 'intervention' to assist the transaction. This systematic approach provides a step by step process for the analysis of the learners' needs, the design and development of the material. There are various instructional design models available. Most of the models involve the process of analysing the learners' needs and goals of the instructional material development, development of a delivery system and content, pilot study of the material developed, implementation, evaluation, refinement of the materials etc. In designing and developing the eContent, a suitable instructional design approach based on our requirements can be adopted. One of the most generic, common and popular approaches for instructional design is ADDIE.

Conclusion:

As a teacher, you have mastered subject and the process of eContent development. You are requested to evaluate the given eContent in respect of objectives, content coverage, sequencing of the content, target group, language etc. in the following - statements related to above mentioned aspects are given. Against each statement five-point scale is given. These are

Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Undecided (U) and Not Applicable (NA). Read each statement carefully and select one out of the given five options, which best describes your decision about the eContent. Try to be as objective as possible during the evaluation of eContent.

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